

Linking Instrument PIDs With Related Research Entities

Guidance Document

PID4NFDI

13 December 2025

Imprint

Authored by	Jana Böhm (https://orcid.org/0009-0004-9802-113X)
Reviewed by	Frederik Springer (https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5379-0059), Sara El-Gebali (https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1378-5495)
Date of publication	13 December 2025
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17535290
License	This work is licensed under https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Deliverable	Part of D3.1 in the integration phase of PID4NFDI

About

PID4NFDI (<https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi>) is the basic service for persistent identifiers in development for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). PID4NFDI is part of and funded through Base4NFDI.

Funded by DFG as part of NFDI. DFG Grant Number: 521453681

Contents

1. Introduction and Overview	1
2. Connections in Detail	8
Persons and Organizations	8
Project	8
Funding	9
Software	9
Other Instruments	10
Instrument Papers	11
Datasets	11
Publications	13
Samples	13
3. Summary	15
4. References	16

1. Introduction and Overview

Instrument persistent identifiers (PIDs) provide the greatest value when they are not only registered but also linked to other relevant research entities. Establishing these connections strengthens discovery, reproducibility and provenance, and makes it possible to trace instrument use across documented research outputs.

This document offers recommendations on how to connect instrument PIDs with PIDs identifying related research entities.

If you are not yet familiar with PIDs for instruments in general, you can find an introduction to the topic in the PID4NFDI Cookbook [1]. For concrete examples on how to fill in the metadata fields of an instrument PID, we refer to [2].

The recommendations in this document assume that instrument PIDs follow the PIDINST metadata schema [3], which is directly adopted by B2INST [4] (a service offered by EUDAT that can be used to assign ePIC PIDs to instruments) and partially mapped to the DataCite metadata schema [5]. As a result, PIDINST and B2INST share the same guidance¹, while DataCite-specific recommendations are provided separately where practices diverge.

Instruments can be associated with a wide range of resources and actors in the research ecosystem, many of which are also identified by PIDs. Examples include:

- **Persons/Organizations:** An instrument might be built, owned or managed by individuals, research groups or a whole institute or organization. Additionally, researchers use instruments as part of their research.
- **Projects:** An instrument can be purchased, built or used in the context of a project.
- **Funding:** An instrument may be acquired or managed using funds obtained from external agencies under a specific grant, or using in-kind support from participating organizations.
- **Software:** The instrument may have software installed which runs on the device.
- **Other Instruments:** Instruments may be related to other instruments, for example if an instrument is a new version of an old instrument, or in the case of a complex instrument that has multiple components which may be considered as instruments themselves.

¹ In the following, we will usually refer to the “PIDINST/B2INST metadata” for brevity. Strictly speaking, PIDINST is the metadata schema and B2INST is the service adopting this schema.

- **Instrument Papers:** Some instruments are described in dedicated publications, sometimes referred to as “instrument papers” [6]. These articles typically appear in specialist journals (e.g., the *Journal of Large-Scale Research Facilities* (JLSRF) [7]), describe the technical details and provide formal recognition for the instrument.
- **Datasets²:** Instruments are used to conduct measurements, which are usually stored as datasets.
- **Publications:** Research outputs, such as journal articles, theses, preprints, conference proceedings or reports, may be based on datasets produced by instruments. Throughout this document, “publication” refers to such text-based outputs, in contrast to instrument papers that describe the instrument itself.
- **Samples:** An instrument may be used to analyze or measure samples.

For all of these entities, there are several considerable ways to connect them with instruments, for example:

- **Multiple link directions:** A link may point from an instrument to another entity (*instrument* → *entity*), from the entity to the instrument (*entity* → *instrument*) or, where appropriate, in both directions (*instrument* ↔ *entity*).
- **Formal citation vs. metadata fields:** Links can be either carried out by entering PIDs of related resources into the PID metadata of an entity (e.g., DataCite, PIDINST, B2INST related identifiers), but also by formal citation from within a resource (i.e., from the text and the list of references in a publication). While citations embedded in references are generally not machine actionable, this is the case for structured metadata fields.
- **Relation types for metadata fields:** Several relation types are available for creating links in PID metadata. Some types are part of both the PIDINST and DataCite metadata schema, such as “References” and “IsDescribedBy”. Others occur in only one of the two schemas, leading to minor differences in recommended usage.

The following sections provide recommendations for linking each of the above entities with instrument PIDs. Different types of PIDs are conceivable for the different entities, such as DataCite DOIs, Crossref DOIs, ePIC PIDs, ORCID IDs, ROR

² The dataset can be stored as simple files/folders or within an ELN. If an ELN is used, in order to publish the dataset, the relevant files are extracted from the ELN and uploaded as a dataset to a repository. Hence, we do not consider ELNs separately here.

IDs, etc. Where relevant, we specify which PID provider a given recommendation refers to when considering the direction *entity* → *instrument*.

Overviews of the recommended connections can be found in Figure 1 and Table 1 below.

Linking Instruments With Related Research Entities: Guidance Document

Related Research Entity	PIDINST/B2INST metadata fields for: instrument → research entity	DataCite metadata fields for: instrument → research entity	research entity → instrument
Person	<i>Owner.ownerIdentifier, Manufacturer.manufacturerIdentifier</i> Here, a person corresponds to the owner or manufacturer of an instrument. Recommended link.	<i>Creator.nameIdentifier, Contributor.nameIdentifier</i> Here, a person corresponds to the owner or manufacturer of an instrument. Recommended link.	An ORCID record may link an instrument PID as a <i>resource item</i> . In this case, the person corresponds to a researcher using an instrument for their research. Optional link.
Organization	<i>Owner.ownerIdentifier, Manufacturer.manufacturerIdentifier</i> Recommended link.	<i>Creator.nameIdentifier, Contributor.nameIdentifier</i> Recommended link.	Link not commonly recorded.
Project	<i>RelatedIdentifier with relationType "WasUsedIn"</i> Recommended link.	<i>RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsPartOf"</i> Recommended link.	If the project PID is registered via DataCite, the <i>relatedIdentifier with relationType "HasPart"</i> can be used to link an instrument. If the project PID is registered with ePIC, there should be an appropriate field in the metadata where the instrument PID can be entered. Optional link.
Funding	<i>RelatedIdentifier with relationType "WasUsedIn"</i> or via a B2INST community extension Recommended link.	<i>FundingReference.funderIdentifier, FundingReference.awardNumber, FundingReference.awardURI</i> Recommended link.	Link not commonly recorded.
Software	<i>RelatedIdentifier with relationType "References"</i>	<i>RelatedIdentifier with relationType "References"</i>	Link not commonly recorded.

Linking Instruments With Related Research Entities: Guidance Document

	or via a B2INST community extension Recommended link.	Recommended link.	
Other Instruments (A is new version of B)	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsPreviousVersionOf" and "IsNewVersionOf". Recommended links.	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsPreviousVersionOf" and "IsNewVersionOf". Recommended links.	(see columns two and three of this row)
Other Instruments (A is part of B)	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsComponentOf" and "HasComponent" Recommended links.	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsPartOf" and "HasPart" Recommended links.	(see columns two and three of this row)
Other Instruments (A and B are permanently attached to each other)	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsAttachedTo" Recommended links.	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsPartOf" Recommended links.	(see columns two and three of this row)
Other Instruments (two PIDs reference the same instrument)	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsIdenticalTo" Recommended links.	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsIdenticalTo" Recommended links.	(see columns two and three of this row)
Instrument Papers	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsDescribedBy" Recommended link.	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsDescribedBy" Recommended link.	Independent of the instrument paper's PID metadata, the instrument paper should formally cite the instrument PID from its list of references. If the instrument paper is registered with DataCite, use the relatedIdentifier with relationType "Describes" . If the instrument paper is registered with ePIC, there should

			be an appropriate field in the metadata where the instrument PID can be entered. Recommended link.
Datasets	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "References" Optional link (often not applicable).	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "Collects" Optional link (often not applicable).	If the dataset PID is registered with DataCite, use relatedIdentifier with relationType "IsCollectedBy" . If the dataset is registered with ePIC, there should be an appropriate field in the metadata where the instrument PID can be entered. Recommended link.
Publications	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "References" Optional link (often not applicable).	RelatedIdentifier with relationType "IsReferencedBy" Optional link (often not applicable).	Independent of the publication's PID metadata, the publication should formally cite the instrument PID from its list of references. If the publication is registered with DataCite, use relatedIdentifier with relationType "References" . If the instrument paper is registered with ePIC, there should be an appropriate field in the metadata where the instrument PID can be entered. Recommended link.

Table 1: Summary of recommended connections between instruments and related research entities.

The second and third columns list the PIDINST/B2INST and DataCite metadata fields, respectively, that can be used to link an instrument PID to other research entities. In addition to the recommended entries shown in the table, some links are marked as "Optional link" or "Link not commonly recorded". These categories provide guidance on optional connections that may support further metadata enrichment but play a less central role or are difficult to consistently record. The final column outlines how a corresponding link from the related research entity back to the instrument can be established. Only connections that directly involve instruments are included; links among other entities (such as samples, publications and datasets) are omitted. Further details and explanatory notes are provided in Section 2. For clarity, the DataCite relation types "References" and "IsReferencedBy" may also be expressed as "Cites" and "IsCitedBy", respectively. These alternatives have been omitted here to maintain readability. Section 2 discusses the connections in more detail.

2. Connections in Detail

Persons and Organizations

Instrument → Person/Organization

Connecting related persons or organizations to an instrument is straightforward because the PIDINST/B2INST metadata schema provides dedicated metadata fields for this purpose: **Owner.ownerIdentifier** for entering a PID identifying an instrument's owner, and **Manufacturer.manufacturerIdentifier** for entering a PID identifying the manufacturer. The corresponding metadata fields in the DataCite metadata schema are **Contributor.nameIdentifier** and **Creator.nameIdentifier**. These fields should be completed by the person responsible for registering the instrument PID. Further details on the interpretation of the owner and manufacturer fields are provided by the PIDINST metadata schema [3].

Person/Organization → Instrument

The link from organizations (identified by ROR IDs) to instruments are generally not captured, as ROR metadata focuses on describing the organization itself rather than associated research resources.

For individuals, an instrument PID may be added to a researcher's ORCID record to indicate use of the instrument in their work. To do so, a **research resource proposal item** needs to be added, under which several instruments can be listed as **resource items**. Detailed instructions can be found in [8].

Project

Instrument → Project

If an instrument is purchased, built or used in the context of a project and the project is identified by a PID, then the instrument should reference the project PID using the **relatedIdentifier** field (available in PIDINST/B2INST and DataCite). The PIDINST/B2INST metadata schema has the **relationType "WasUsedIn"** specifically for this purpose. If the instrument is registered with DataCite, the **relationType "IsPartOf"** should be used to link a project PID.

Project → Instrument

When a project PID is registered with DataCite, the **relatedIdentifier field with relationType "HasPart"** can be used to link an instrument to the project. If the project PID is registered with ePIC, there should be a field in the metadata where

the instrument PID can be entered appropriately. However, creating a link from the project to the instrument requires that the individual registering the project PID is aware of the instrument PID, which might not always be the case. Hence, we consider this relation as optional (it is “nice to have”, but not always feasible to record).

Funding

Instrument → Funding

If an instrument is procured or managed using funding identified by a PID, this PID can be linked from the PIDINST/B2INST schema via a **relatedIdentifier with relationType “WasUsedIn”**. In cases where funding lacks a PID, or consists of in-kind support, the PIDINST/B2INST metadata schema does not provide a direct way to record this information. However, if the instrument is registered with B2INST, an additional metadata field can be added as a community extension to capture both the PID (or identifying information) of the funding agency/supporting organization and the grant number.

For instruments registered with DataCite, the metadata field **FundingReference** should be used:

- **FundingReference.funderIdentifier** for the PID of the funding agency,
- **FundingReference.awardNumber** for the grant number, and
- **FundingReference.awardURI** for the grant PID, if available.

Funding → Instrument

This connection is not commonly recorded.

Software

Instrument → Software

Software running on an instrument may be identified by a PID or, more commonly, by an URL (e.g., to a GitHub repository). Such identifiers can be added to the instrument record using the **relatedIdentifier with relationType “References”** both in the PIDINST/B2INST and the DataCite schema. “References” is the generic relation type in the PIDINST schema, to be used when no other type fits, which is the case here. B2INST users may also choose to include software information via a community extension instead to improve interpretability.

Software → Instrument

This connection is not commonly recorded.

Other Instruments

Instrument ↔ Instrument

There are various conceivable connections between research instruments. Let A and B denote two distinct instruments.

1. New/old version

If an instrument is substantially modified, a new PID should be attributed to the instrument [3]. With A referring to the new instrument PID and B referring to the old instrument PID, both PIDs should be connected via **relatedIdentifiers**. The PIDINST/B2INST and the DataCite metadata schema both have the **relationTypes** “*IsPreviousVersionOf*” and “*IsNewVersionOf*”.

- A → B: use “*IsNewVersionOf*”
- B → A: use “*IsPreviousVersionOf*”

2. Parts of instruments

An instrument may be complex, having multiple components that may be considered as instruments themselves. In this case, the parts should be linked to the compound instrument via **relatedIdentifiers**. The PIDINST/B2INST metadata schema has the **relationTypes** “*IsComponentOf*” / “*HasComponent*” and the DataCite metadata schema has the equivalent pair “*IsPartOf*” / “*HasPart*”. With A referring to the compound instrument and B referring to a part:

- A → B: use “*HasComponent*” / “*HasPart*”
- B → A: use “*IsComponentOf*” / “*IsPartOf*”

3. Permanently attached instruments

When two instruments are permanently attached to each other, this should be captured in the PIDINST/B2INST metadata using the **relatedIdentifiers** with **relationType** “*IsAttachedTo*” in both PIDs. DataCite provides no direct equivalent. The closest relation type is “*IsPartOf*”, which can be used in this case.

4. Duplicate PIDs

Situations in which an instrument has been assigned multiple PIDs should be avoided, but when they occur, both PID records should be updated to

reference each other using ***relatedIdentifiers with relationType "IsIdenticalTo"***. This is supported by both PIDINST/B2INST and DataCite.

Instrument Papers

For some instruments (for example, the beamlines and experiment stations at BESSY II³), articles are published in specialist journals which describe the technical details of the instrument. These publications, referred to as “instrument papers” [6], should be linked to the instrument through a bidirectional connection.

Instrument → Instrument Paper

The instrument PID should link the instrument paper in its metadata record via the ***relatedIdentifier field using the relationType "IsDescribedBy"***. This relation type is supported by both PIDINST/B2INST and DataCite.

Instrument Paper → Instrument

The other way around, the instrument paper should ***formally cite*** the instrument PID in the text and in the reference list, regardless of which PID type is assigned to the paper.

If the instrument paper is registered with DataCite, additionally, the ***relatedIdentifier with relationType "Describes"*** should be used to link the instrument. In case that a Crossref DOI is used, the instrument reference should be included into the Crossref metadata record. In case that an ePIC PID is assigned to the instrument paper, make sure that there is an appropriate metadata field in the PID metadata of the instrument paper.

Establishing these links requires coordination between the authors of the instrument paper and the individual responsible for registering the instrument PID.

Datasets

Dataset → Instrument

Ideally, datasets should explicitly reference the instrument used to generate them: If the dataset PID is registered with DataCite, it should reference the instrument PID via the DataCite ***relatedIdentifier with relationType "IsCollectedBy"***. If the dataset is registered with ePIC, there should be a field in the metadata where the instrument PID is entered appropriately.

³ BESSY II: The Helmholtz Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie (HZB) operates the BESSY II synchrotron radiation source, see [9].

However, it is not always possible to achieve this ideal state using the repositories and workflows currently in place, for several reasons.

1. To publish a dataset PID, a researcher typically uploads the dataset to a research data repository. Depending on the repository software and implementation, there may be no metadata fields in which the researcher can meaningfully enter instrument PIDs. Even if these fields exist, the information may not be passed on correctly to the relevant DataCite/ePIC metadata fields due to the repository's non-optimal setup. We recommend that repository managers ensure their repository offers fields to enter instrument PIDs⁴, and to verify that these are correctly passed on to DataCite/ePIC.
2. Researchers may not be aware that they can (and should) enter an instrument PID when depositing a dataset. We recommend adding a short explanation to the instrument's landing page how a researcher should link/cite the instrument PID.

Nonetheless, recording this link where possible remains important.

Instrument → Dataset

Depending on the use-case, the instrument PID may contain a reference to the dataset PID via the PIDINST/B2INST ***relatedIdentifier with relationType "References"*** or the DataCite ***relatedIdentifier with relationType "Collects"***.

A link from the instrument to the dataset can be considered optional. As instrument PIDs are often registered centrally and are potentially re-used very frequently by different researchers, it would require significant effort for the registering organization to continually collect all the datasets that were outputs of this instrument and enter them regularly into the instrument PID. This approach simply does not scale well. However, if your use case is suitable for this approach, e.g. if instruments are mainly used by a small group of researchers, it may also be possible to establish *instrument* → *dataset* links.

Calibrations and Configurations

Calibration and configuration details play a critical role in ensuring accurate measurements. Calibrations are often made before the measurement process begins, and configurations (e.g. setting software parameters, selecting a specific

⁴ This could be a metadata field that specifically captures instrument PIDs (which may be especially useful for research disciplines that often use instruments), but it could also be a general field to reference any kind of related resources.

measurement mode or adapting physical arrangements) significantly impact the outcome and reproducibility of measurements. Calibrations and configurations should **not** be entered into the instrument PID. Instead, they belong directly to the dataset and should be recorded in the files uploaded to the research data repository.

Publications

Instrument → Publication

The instrument PID may link a publication via the PIDINST/B2INST ***relatedIdentifier field with relationType “References”***. If the instrument PID is registered with DataCite, the DataCite ***relatedIdentifier with relationType “IsReferencedBy”*** should be used.

As with datasets, it may not be feasible to collect all publications that rely on a particular instrument. Therefore, the connection from the instrument to the publication is optional.

Publication → Instrument

The other way around, the publication should ***formally cite*** the instrument PID from within its text and list of references, regardless of the PID type assigned to the publication.

Similar challenges to those encountered when connecting to datasets also apply when connecting publications with instruments. Researchers may not be aware that they can cite an instrument PID. We recommend providing a citation suggestion on the instrument's landing page.

If the publication is registered with DataCite, additionally, the ***relatedIdentifier with relationType “References”*** should be used to link the instrument. In case that a Crossref DOI is used, the instrument reference should be included into the Crossref metadata record. In case that an ePIC PID is assigned to the publication, make sure that there is an appropriate metadata field in PID metadata of the instrument paper.

Samples

A sample may be registered with a PID (e.g. IGSN, DOI, ePIC PID). If an instrument is used to conduct measurements on samples (resulting in datasets), a set of samples may be attributed to an instrument. We recommend connecting the sample to the relevant outputs which were generated based on the sample, such as datasets and

publications. However, directly linking samples to instruments is not recommended, for the following reasons:

- Neither the PIDINST/B2INST nor the DataCite metadata schema provides a fitting relation type to connect samples and instruments. Hence, any connections between samples and instruments would be difficult to interpret.
- If samples are anyway connected to datasets and publications, and these are, in turn, connected to instruments, the connections between samples and instruments are already captured implicitly.

Sample → Dataset/Publication

A sample should link a dataset or publication via DataCite ***relatedIdentifier with relationType "IsReferencedBy"***. If an ePIC PID is used for the sample, make sure that an appropriate metadata field containing links to the datasets and publications is added.

Dataset/Publication → Sample

Conversely, the publication should ***formally cite*** the sample PID. Additionally, the dataset/publication should link the instrument PID via ***relatedIdentifier with relationType "References"*** if it is registered with DataCite. If an ePIC PID is used, ensure that an appropriate metadata field containing a link to the sample is added. In case that a Crossref DOI is used, the instrument reference should be included into the Crossref metadata record.

3. Summary

This document provides recommendations on how instrument PIDs can be linked to other research entities, including persons, organizations, projects, funding, software, other instruments, instrument papers, datasets, publications, and samples. Establishing these connections remains challenging because instrument PIDs are still emerging within the research community and are not yet consistently recognized across workflows. Multiple stakeholder groups, such as researchers, instrument specialists, and repository managers, contribute to creating these links, each with different roles and levels of familiarity with PID practices. To support the establishment of robust PID connections, the following measures are recommended:

- **For those responsible for instrument landing pages:** Include clear guidance on how the instrument should be cited and linked from datasets, instrument papers and publications.
- **For those registering instrument PIDs:** Ensure that person and organization PIDs are included, as well as relations to software, funding, projects, and other instruments, where applicable. Maintain communication with instrument scientists regarding instrument papers, and, where an overview of associated research outputs exists, consider adding relevant publications and datasets to the instrument PID.
- **For repository managers:** Provide metadata fields for instrument PIDs within repository submission forms and ensure that these fields are correctly mapped to the corresponding PID provider.
- **For researchers:** Consult the instrument's landing page for citation and linking instructions. Where repository metadata fields are available, record the instrument PID when depositing datasets, and formally cite the instrument in any resulting publications.

4. References

- [1] PID4NFDI Cookbook - PID for Instruments:
<https://pid4nfdi-training.readthedocs.io/en/latest/pidinst.html> (accessed 5.11.2025)
- [2] Edmunds, R., Springer, F., Böhm, J., & El-Gebali, S. (2025). Metadata Examples for Instrument PIDs: Guidance Document. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17535689>
- [3] Krahl, R., Darroch, L., Huber, R., Devaraju, A., Klump, J., Habermann, T., Stocker, M., & RDA PIDINST WG Members. (2022). 'Metadata Schema for the Persistent Identification of Instruments' (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00070>
- [4] B2INST: <https://b2inst.gwdg.de/> (accessed 5.11.2025)
- [5] DataCite metadata schema:
<https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/> (accessed 5.11.2025)
- [6] Stocker, M., Darroch, L., Krahl, R., Habermann, T., Devaraju, A., Schwarzmann, U., D'Onofrio, C. and Häggström, I. (2020) 'Persistent Identification of Instruments', Data Science Journal, 19(1), p. 18. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-018>
- [7] Journal of large-scale research facilities JLRFS: <https://jlsrf.org/index.php/lrf> (accessed 5.11.2025)
- [8] Research resources on your ORCID record:
<https://support.orcid.org/hc/en-us/articles/360011433613-Research-resources-on-your-ORCID-record> (accessed 5.11.2025)
- [9] Röntgenquelle BESSY II:
https://www.helmholtz-berlin.de/forschung/quellen/bessy/index_de.html (accessed 5.11.2025)